

Preliminary Literature Review on Recent Research in Seismic Performance of Tunnel Structures

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1. Introduction

In the United States alone, there are estimated to be 337 highway tunnels and 211 transit tunnels (NCHRP 2006). These assets are vulnerable to a wide range of threats, including natural disasters, intentional attacks, and accidents. The focus of this report is on the performance of underground transportation infrastructure during earthquakes and recent research in that area covering post-earthquake damage assessments, shake table tests, and numerical analyses (Table 1). Generally, the response of tunnel systems to seismically induced ground motion can be described by three types of deformation: axial deformation of the tunnel, curvature of the tunnel, and ovaling or racking of the cross-section. Generally, tunnel structures are less vulnerable to seismic shaking than surface structure and are able to maintain their structural integrity during seismic motion (NCHRP 2006). This is true so long as there is minimal ground deformation and the ground remains stable. In these cases, the surrounding ground confines the underground structure and moves with the tunnel system. However, situations such as soft ground, slope instability, fault crossing and structural irregularities (e.g., cross passages) merit special consideration.

Following this introduction, section two summarizes analysis methods employed by the papers reviewed in this report. The subsequent three sections summarize the findings in the areas of post-

disaster investigations, shake table testing, and analytical modeling. This report was completed as a semester-long independent study project. Because of the limited time, there were several references that were not reviewed, but that nonetheless appear to be important. These are listed at the end of the report for future consideration.

Table 1: Overview of Topics Covered by the Papers Reviewed in this Report

Reference	Section	Type of Model	Feature studied? (✓ = yes)							
			Tunnel Section	Lining	Slope at Tunnel Entrance	Cross-Structure	Cross-Passage	Fault Zone	Joint	Soft Ground
Jiang (2013)	Circular	Shake Table		✓	✓			✓		
Jiao (2013)	Circular	Numerical					✓			
Yu (2017b)	Rectangular	Shake Table	✓							✓
Kontoe (2008)	Circular	Numerical	✓	✓						
Geng (2013)	Circular	Numerical	✓							✓
Yu (2017a)	Circular	Numerical	✓	✓						✓
Fabozzi (2016)	Circular	Numerical		✓						
Tao (2013)	Rectangular	Shake Table	✓			✓				
Luzhen (2010)	Rectangular	Both	✓							
Sen (2013)	General	General								

2. Seismic Performance

This section includes observations gathered during the Wenchuan earthquake of 2008, the Kobe earthquake of 1995 and the Duzce earthquake of 1999. The Wenchuan earthquake caused lining cracks, lining dislocation, and even the collapse or embedment of entire tunnels, the Longxi tunnel collapsed during this event (Geng et al 2013 & Yu et al 2017a); Geng et al. (2013) observed 45° cracks crossing the section of the tunnel. Subsequent analysis was conducted and was found to be consistent with the observed behavior of the tunnel. The Kobe earthquake caused significant damage to more than 100 tunnels. During this event, some columns in a subway failed, leading to ground settlement (Geng et al 2013).

The Duzce earthquake inflicted severe damage and in some cases collapse of underground structures. Kontoe et al. (2008) reported on the Bolu highway twin tunnels that experienced the Duzce earthquake during construction. Some portions under construction suffered severe damage up to and including collapse. Some completed portions performed poorly due to poor ground conditions (fault gouge clay). Kontoe et al. conducted analytical studies to understand the failure mechanisms. These studies, which were in good agreement with field observations, are summarized later in the report.

3. Shake Table Tests

Sen et al. (2013) present a general overview of shake table testing of tunnels. They pay attention to five aspects: the possible shake table arrangements, the simulation material, the similarity ratio of the material, the construction of the testing box, and the data acquisition method. Sen et al. identify three types of shake tables: ordinary shaking tables, shaking table arrays and centrifuge shakers, which are able to simulate actual stress conditions. The dynamic characteristics of the modeled ground heavily influence seismic response. Because different properties scale differently, it is recommended to focus on the main aspects of the material to minimize errors in the similarity relation between the model and the prototype. There are three common types of boxes: laminar shear box, flexible wall barrel, and rigid wall box. The laminar shear box can model the soil boundary conditions and is ideal for minimizing the reflection and scattering effect of waves on the boundary. The rigid wall box is used in mountain tunnel modeling as the characteristics of the box allow for simplicity and easy to pour materials. Typical data acquisition measurements include pressure, displacement, strain, and acceleration.

Luzhen et al. (2010) studied underground utility tunnels with shake table testing and finite element analysis. Their experimental setup consisted of a laminar shear box on a shake table. The laminar shear box had overall dimension of 3.0 m long, 1.8 m wide and 1.91 m high. The model has 3000 mm x 3000 mm cross sections with 300 mm thick walls. The shake table was excited horizontally with the El-Centro earthquake at varying intensities and a sine wave excitation of acceleration amplitude of 1.0 g. Luzhen et al. observed that the acceleration response of the structure was slightly lower than that of the surrounding soil. They also observed that the maximum internal force was at the corners of the cross-section.

Yu et al. (2017a) conducted a multi-point shaking table test of a scaled long tunnel. The objectives of the experiment were to investigate the acceleration response of the tunnel and the

deformation of the tunnel joints. The specimen was based on a 5,670 m long immersed tunnel at the time under construction as part of the Hong Kong-Zhuhai-Macau Bridge project. The experiment consisted of an array of twelve connected model boxes connected by four independent shake tables with a dimension of 4 m x 6 m each. The experiment focused on the connections between the model boxes, the soil and the tunnel structure. Four “active” boxes were placed on the four shaking tables, while the remaining eight “inactive” boxes provided continuity between the active boxes. The inactive boxes were supported by steel frames. The specimen soil modeled the bed of 60 meter-thick silty sand layer below the tunnel. The similitude ratio for the relative stiffness of the soil and the structure was calibrated to provide the correct relative stiffness between the soil and the structure. Based on these considerations, aluminum was chosen for the tunnel specimen with silicon strips to act as connections between the segments. Under non-uniform excitation, the test specimens experienced significant deformation at the joints. For example, test 2 was conducted under non-uniform acceleration in the longitudinal direction and was plotted against joint displacement and the tunnel elements at times 0.000 s, 0.035 s, 0.070 s, and 0.105 s. It is apparent that the deformations increased with time and decreased as the wave passed along the tunnel elements. The initial segment E2 experience a displacement of about 0.017 in., while the last member E12 experienced a displacement of about -0.0006 in. Additionally, the tunnel experienced a stronger dynamic response than the soil.

Tao et al. (2013) investigated a cross-structure between a subway station and the tunnel. The experiment consisted of a suspended laminar shear model box tested on a 3.0 m x 3.0 m shake table. Three scenarios were conducted. The first scenario tested the station alone. The second and third tests consisted of a station resting on top a tunnel structure separated by 0 cm and 15 cm gaps, respectively. The tunnel was found to absorb the earthquake waves, thus reducing the seismic response of the upper station structure. The amount of reduction varied with the thickness of the interlayer soil between the station and the tunnel.

Jiang et al. (2013) investigated the mechanical behavior of a tunnel lining passing through a fault. This test is modeled after a tunnel in the junction of the Himalayan and Hengduan Mountains of southeastern Tibetan Plateau after the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake. The focus points of these tests are the fault segment, entrance lining and the slope around the tunnel entrance. Observed damage included the destruction of the lining in the segment crossing the fault and serious damage to the right shoulder of the lining. Longitudinal cracks appeared at the left shoulder and inverted

arch. Horizontal and vertical cracks along the slope appear in the surface above the tunnel. The behavior and failure mechanism were consistent with the actual earthquake damage.

4. Analytical Models

As described in the previous section, Luzhen et al. (2010) conducted shake table tests to analyze an underground utility tunnel. In support of these tests, they also conducted analyses using linear finite elements methods. The analysis focused on the three main factors: the laminar shear box, soil-structure interaction, and the initial stress field. The numerical results were found to be in good agreement with the experimental measurements. The analyses further suggested that the maximum strain distribution on a side slab is different from the top or outer slab. The outer slab experienced larger strains at the corner and smaller strains at the mid-height of the slab, while the strains in the top slab were concentrated at the middle. The dynamic earth pressure was assumed to be an important effect on underground utility tunnel damage when triggered by a seismic wave. As the numerical results showed that the dynamic earth pressured is the main factor in underground utility tunnel damage.

Kontoe et al. (2008) studied the seismic tunnel response of the Bolu highway twin tunnels during the 1999 Duzce earthquake. The purpose of this numerical study was to compare the results of both static and finite element analyses with the post-earthquake field observations. The report focused on two sections of the Bolu highway twin tunnels located at chainage 62+850 and 62+870. These sections considered the right bench pilot tunnel (RBPT) and left bench pilot tunnel (LBPT). Comparisons between the dynamic analyses and the simplified analytical elastic solutions were made. It was concluded that the 2D FE analyses cannot properly model the tunnel structure as the findings were not consistent with the observed post-earthquake damage of the tunnel. The extended Hoeg method was used to predict hoop stress and was consistent with the dynamic FE analyses as well as the post-earthquake observations. The tunnels deformed predominantly in an oval shape with maxima of the thrust, bending moment, and hoop stress occurring at the shoulder and knee locations, which are located roughly at 137° and 317° around the circular tunnel lining. This was in good agreement with the post-earthquake field observations.

Geng et al. (2013) compared the application of two methods of analysis to a subway shield tunnel in soft ground. The earthquake coefficient method uses a horizontal seismic coefficient determined by the peak ground acceleration of the earthquake. This coefficient, tunnel weight, overburden soil pressure, and lateral earth pressure are used to determine the equivalent seismic

force applied to the tunnel. The seismic deformation method was developed after several studies showed that the response of tunnels differed from that of the ground. This method used the ground displacement and shear stress to calculate the internal forces in a tunnel structure. Both methods were applied to obtain estimates of bending moment, axial force, and shear force. The maximum positive bending was consistent across models, lying on the vertex-right 45° with similar distributions of moments. When examining the axial and shear force there was a difference in the distribution of forces. The earthquake coefficient method transforms the seismic effect into a horizontal seismic force and transfers the load into the tunnel. So the entire structure experiences a single compression state. While the seismic deformation method divides the seismic load into the ground displacement in the form of forced displacement and surrounding shear stress. This allows the tunnel to experience both tension and compression states. It was concluded that the seismic deformation method was a better representation of the model during earthquake excitation, as the characteristics of the seismic deformation method are more appropriate in modeling the behavior of shield tunnels in soft ground.

Fabozzi et al. (2016) investigated the performance of continuous and segmental linings of shallow tunnels under seismic loading. A circular tunnel lining with nonlinear properties was modeled with finite element full dynamic analyses. Full dynamic analyses takes into consideration the existing stress state around the tunnel and the permanent ground deformation during shaking to evaluate the change of internal forces in a tunnel lining. The numerical model was validated by a centrifuge test conducted by other researchers. Once validated, the model was used to investigate effects of the construction process and segmental layout. The results indicated significantly lower internal forces of the jointed pattern of a segmental lining compared to a continuous lining

Jiao et al. (2013) built a numerical model to investigate the effects of cross passages in tunnels. The FLAC^{3D} program was used to evaluate the effects of cross passages to the longitudinal seismic response of the tunnel. FLAC^{3D} uses an explicit finite difference scheme to solve the equations of motion, allowing the dynamic analysis of soil-structure interaction. The results show that the cross passage can help reduce the response of the longitudinal acceleration, but there are higher shear stress concentrations at the intersection. Through the use of the response displacement method, it was concluded that the geology imposes significant effects on stability and dynamic response of the intersections at cross passages.

In a more general vein, Yu et al. (2017b) presented an evaluation of simplified and unified methods for analysis currently in use for tunnels. Simplified methods were subdivided into mass-spring-beam models and beam-spring model, while unified methods were subdivided into continuum-based multiscale coupling method and discrete-continuum multiscale coupling method. Simplified methods allow insight into the behavior of the structure and provide first estimates for preliminary design. With simplified methods, there are limitations due to simplifying assumptions. Multiscale methods are high fidelity methodologies but incur a greater computational expense.

5. Acknowledgment

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